

Evaluating Antimicrobial Potentials of Herbal Remedies in Urinary Tract Infections

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are part and parcel of human society to combat diseases from the dawn of civilization. According to World Health Organization (WHO), about 80% of the world population rely chiefly on plant based traditional medicine specially for their primary health care needs and there has been a worldwide move towards the use of traditional medicines due to concerns over the more invasive, expensive and potentially toxic main stream practices. This review gives a bird's eye view on the updated information on urinary tract infections (UTIs), different categories of urologic herbs, historical use and modern scientific investigations on some important urologic herbs, clinical studies, some isolated chemical compounds and their possible side effects.

Keywords: Medicinal plants; Urinary Tract Infections ; Historical use; Scientific analysis ; Clinical studies ; Bioactive constituents; Possible side effects.

INTRODUCTION

UTI may be asymptomatic. However, some patients report incontinence, a general lack of well-being, or both¹. Cystitis clinically manifests as irritative voiding symptoms that include frequent and painful urination of small amounts of turbid urine, urgency, suprapubic or lower abdominal pain, and incontinence. Fever tends to be absent in infections limited to the lower urinary tract. In men, urinary retention should be ruled out, because it is frequently associated with cystitis and possible prostatitis. The manifestations of UTI in older adults may include confusion, lethargy, anorexia, and incontinence. The absence of dysuria, and the presence of vaginal discharge significantly decrease the probability of UTI². Lower urinary tract infection is also referred to as a bladder infection. The most common symptoms are burning with urination and having to urinate frequently (or an urge to urinate) in the absence of vaginal discharge and significant pain³. These symptoms may vary from mild to severe⁴ and in healthy women last an average of six days⁵. Some pain above the pubic bone or in the lower back may be present. People experiencing an upper urinary tract infection, or pyelonephritis, may experience flank pain, fever, or nausea and vomiting in addition to the classic symptoms of a lower urinary tract infection⁴. Rarely the urine may appear bloody or contain visible pus in the urine⁵. In young children, the only symptom of a urinary tract infection (UTI) may be a fever. Because of the lack of more obvious symptoms, when females under the age of two or uncircumcised males less than a year exhibit a fever, a culture of the urine is recommended by *Author for Correspondence: imad_dna@yahoo.com many medical associations. Infants may feed poorly, vomit, sleep more, or show signs of jaundice. In older children, new onset urinary incontinence (loss of bladder control) may occur⁶. Urinary tract symptoms are frequently lacking in the elderly⁷. The presentations may be vague with incontinence, a change in mental status, or fatigue as the

only symptoms⁴, while some present to a health care provider with sepsis, an infection of the blood, as the first symptoms⁸. Diagnosis can be complicated by the fact that many elderly people have preexisting incontinence or dementia⁷. It is reasonable to obtain a urine culture in those with signs of systemic infection that may be unable to report urinary symptoms, such as when advanced dementia is present. Systemic signs of infection include a fever or increase in temperature of more than 1.1 °C (2.0 °F) from usual, chills, and an increase white blood cell count.

Anatomical and physiological factors

Among several factors contributing to the risk of acquiring UTIs, anatomical and physiological factors are predisposing to UTI. Urinary tract abnormalities affecting the flow of urine and emptying of the bladder increase the risk of UTI. Urine voiding disorders such as those associated with prolapse, multiple sclerosis, bladder cancer, or bladder stones increase the risk⁹. Women with any urinary tract abnormality are more prone to pyelonephritis refractory to oral therapy or complicated by bacteraemia. This is due, in part, to the female anatomy in that a much shorter urethra allows pathogens easier access to the bladder¹⁰. Constipation increases the residue after micturition, causes functional obstruction and affects the flow of urine^{11,12}.

Age

UTI affects people in varying incidences depending on age group. The incidence of UTI is highest during the first year of life and peaking again during adolescence. Approximately 3 % of prepubertal girls and 1 % of prepubertal boys are diagnosed with a UTI. Bacteriuria is more common at the extremes of life¹³. In women after the menopause vaginal prolapsed changes in vaginal flora and urinary incontinence contribute to the increased susceptibility to UTIs¹⁴.

Sex

Gender is an important factor in UTI. Women are much more susceptible than men to community-acquired UTIs except in association with anatomic or functional abnormalities in the first year of life¹⁵. In young sexually active women, sexual activity is the cause of 75–90% of bladder infections, with the risk of infection related to the frequency of sex³. The term "honeymoon cystitis" has been applied to this phenomenon of frequent UTIs during early marriage. In post-menopausal women, sexual activity does not affect the risk of developing a UTI. Spermicide use, independent of sexual frequency, increases the risk of UTIs¹⁶. Diaphragm use is also associated¹⁷. Condom use without spermicide or use of birth control pills does not increase the risk of uncomplicated urinary tract infection³. Women are more prone to UTIs than men because, in females, the urethra is much shorter and closer to the anus¹⁸. As a woman's estrogen levels decrease with menopause, her risk of urinary tract infections increases due to the loss of protective vaginal flora. Additionally, vaginal atrophy that can sometimes occur after menopause is associated with recurrent urinary tract infections¹⁹.

Chronic prostatitis may cause recurrent urinary tract infections in males. Risk of infections increases as males age. While bacteria is commonly present in the urine of older males this does not appear to affect the risk of urinary tract infections²⁰.

Pregnancy

Pregnancy is one of the factors which increase the risk of UTI partly due to the pressure of gravid uterus on the ureters causing stasis of urine flow and is also attributed to the humoral and immunological changes during normal pregnancy^{21,22}. UTI is common with varying prevalence by age, sexual activity and the presence of genitourinary abnormalities²³. In pregnancy UTI carries risk of foetal loss, pre-term labour, intrauterine growth retardation, maternal anemia and also the chance of recurrent infections²⁴.

Chronic Medical Condition

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is a major problem in diabetics. The risk of developing infection in diabetic patients is higher and urinary tract is the most common site for infection¹⁶. Changes in host defense mechanisms, the presence of diabetic cystopathy and micro-vascular disease in the kidneys may play a role in the higher incidence of UTI in diabetic patients. Different medical condition like kidney problem, neurogenic bladder, sickle cell anemia, immune system problem like HIV patient and urinary tract abnormality are also increase the risk for UTIS²⁵. *Urinary catheters*

Urinary catheterization increases the risk for urinary tract infections. The risk of bacteriuria (bacteria in the urine) is between three and six percent per day and prophylactic antibiotics are not effective in decreasing symptomatic infections¹⁸. The risk of an associated infection can be decreased by catheterizing only when necessary, using aseptic technique for insertion, and maintaining unobstructed closed drainage of the catheter^{26,27}. Male scuba divers utilizing condom catheters or the female divers utilizing external catching device for their dry suits are also susceptible to urinary tract infections²⁸.

Others Factors

A predisposition for bladder infections may run in families. Other risk factors include diabetes³, being uncircumcised, and having a large prostate⁴. Complicating factors are rather vague and include predisposing anatomic, functional, or metabolic abnormalities. In children UTIs are associated with vesicoureteral reflux (an abnormal movement of urine from the bladder into ureters or kidneys) and constipation. Persons with spinal cord injury are at increased risk for urinary tract infection in part because of chronic use of catheter, and in part because of voiding dysfunction²⁹. It is the most common cause of infection in this population, as well as the most common cause of hospitalization. Additionally, use of cranberry juice or cranberry supplement appears to be ineffective in prevention and treatment in this population²⁹.

Antimicrobial peptides

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are small cationic proteins produced by white cells and epithelial cells as antibiotics, when the innate immune system is challenged by pathogens. AMPs have a wide antimicrobial spectrum that includes bacteria, virus, and fungus. The antimicrobial function of AMPs is associated with electric charge, secondary structure, and amphiphilic characteristics³⁰. Increased electric charge of AMPs strongly attracts the negative charge of microbial membranes. Amphipathicity is a characteristic that derives from hydrophilic and hydrophobic amino acid of AMPs that facilitates interaction with hydrophilic conditions and hydrophobic microbial membranes³¹. Secondary structure can modify antimicrobial function by 3-dimensional structure. These characteristics make AMPs stick to microorganism, block microbial binding, trigger other components of immune system, and weaken membrane of microorganism. AMPs bind to the negatively charged microbial membrane by the cationic portion, thus inhibiting membrane function and causing death of microorganisms. Some AMPs influence cellular protein or DNA synthesis by passing the cell membrane³¹. Because of these effects, AMPs are regarded as potential therapeutics for drug resistance. AMPs have some desirable properties. AMPs show antimicrobial function at low density. Because microorganisms cannot change their cell membrane easily, they maintain susceptibility to AMPs. AMPs surmount weakness of antibiotics that lose their ability to permeabilize cell membranes³². AMPs display synergistic effects with antibiotics [33]. Despite the broad dispersion in nature, not many AMPs are known to exist in the kidney and urinary tract. AMPs of urinary tract are defensins, cathelicidin, hepcidin, and ribonuclease 7 (RNase 7). AMPs of kidney and urinary tract are THP, lactoferrin, lipocalin and secretory leukocyte proteinase inhibitor³¹. AMPs can kill bacteria by disrupting the microbial membrane (A–C) or translocating across the membrane and binding to intracellular targets (D). Models of membrane disruption include the following: (A) Barrel-stave model: (A1) Cationic AMPs (+) bind to the negatively charged bacteria lipid bilayer (–) and disrupt the microbial membrane by forming an aqueous channel or “barrelstave” (A2). (B) Carpet Model: AMPs blanket the microbial membrane and disrupt it by forming micelles. (C) Torodial Pore Model: AMPs bind to phospholipid head group on the microbial membrane allowing its hydrophobic portion to intercalate

into the microbial membrane and cause the lipid bilayer to fold back on itself³³⁻⁴⁷.

Defensins

Defensins are one of the AMPs that attack bacteria, virus, fungus and protozoans³⁴. Defensins not only attack foreign cells directly but also attract immature dendritic cells³¹. In humans, defensins are classed as α -defensins or β -defensins by their disulfide bridge pattern. Some genes of α -defensins and β -defensins are encoded in chromosome 8p22 and 8p23, but regions of other genes display variations from 2 to 14 per diploid genome.

Hepcidin

Hepcidin (liver expressed antimicrobial peptide1, LEAP1) is made in liver and secreted in the urinary tract. LEAP-1 is related to iron homeostasis and overexpressed LEAP-1 results in severe iron deficiency⁴⁸. LEAP-1 has broad spectrum as a bactericide and its function derives from direct antimicrobial effect and reduction of usable iron that is needed for bacterial survival⁴⁹.

Ribonuclease 7

RNase 7 was initially found in epidermis and subsequently found in bladder, ureter and kidney⁵⁰. Concentration of RNase 7 is higher than other AMPs and shows sufficient bactericidal effect. Rapid and strong action of RNase 7 from Gram positive and negative bacteria results from distraction of cell membrane, that is independent with ribonuclease activity³⁹. Antimicrobial processes of RNase 7 are not fully identified.

Lactoferrin and Lipocalin

Lactoferrin is found in distal collecting tubules. It causes chelation of iron and modification of membrane integrity^{50,51}. Lipocalin reduces siderophore-iron of bacteria and shows bacteriostatic function. Mice without lipocalin are more susceptible to bacteria that utilized siderophores⁵².

Tamm-Horsfall Protein

THP, the most plentiful protein in human urine, is secreted in the loop of Henle⁵³. THP does not have bactericidal activity itself, but blocks bacterial binding to epithelium and promotes bacterial wash-out by urine. THP activates dendrite cells by a TLR4 dependent mechanism.

Diagnosis

The diagnosis of UTIs begins with the screening of patients clinically suspected of having urinary tract infection due to their claiming with problems suggestive of UTIs by a physician. In straightforward cases, a diagnosis may be made and treatment given based on symptoms alone without further laboratory confirmation¹⁶. In complicated or questionable cases, urinalysis may be useful to confirm the diagnosis⁵⁴⁻⁵⁷.

Urine Test

Urine testing is the second important element in diagnostic testing.

Urine collection

Several studies have dealt with the necessity of collecting midstream urine and of cleaning the perineum and vulva or glans penis⁵⁸⁻⁷⁵. However, these were mostly with fairly young and otherwise healthy women, so it is not clear whether they can be transferred to normal clinical practice. A pragmatic solution would be to make the method of urine collection dependent on the clinical problem. For an initial urine investigation with a dip stick, fresh spontaneous urine

can be taken rather than midstream urine and it is unnecessary to clean the genitals. On the other hand, additional studies and urine culture require that the urine sample should be collected and processed with as little contamination as possible.

Practical test methods

The gold standard for a urine test is to perform a bacteriological urine culture, with identification of the pathogen, with quantification and sensitivity testing. To test whether the patient has a UTI at all, orientating indirect methods are often used in practice to detect the bacteria or inflammation (dipsticks). The bacterial count may be assessed by urine microscopy and immersion culture media.

A. Urine dipstick

Urinalysis involves a combination of a dipstick test and urine culture. The dipstick assay was first developed in the 1920s to assess for the presence nitrites, which are present as a result of bacterial growth. Dipstick tests have advanced into multiplexed sample analysis strips with 10 readouts capable of characterizing: (1) specific gravity, (2) pH, (3) nitrites, (4) leukocyte, (5) protein, (6) glucose, (7) urobilirubin, (8) bilirubin, (9) ketones and (10) erythrocytes. Tests are available to quickly check for purulent material or bacteria in the urine, but the tests are most effective if high levels of bacteria are present. False positives are rare, but false negative readings may occur, so a dipstick urine examination should be confirmed with urinalysis, which can detect lower levels of bacteria. Dipsticks test for leukocyte esterase and/or nitrates. The nitrate dipstick test is more accurate than the leukocyte esterase test, but dipsticks that check for both are most accurate. With the nitrate dipstick, false negatives may result if diuresis has decreased urinary nitrate level, if there is inadequate intake of dietary nitrates, or if infections are caused by enterococci or acinetobacter because these bacteria do not produce nitrates. Usually, a high nitrate level indicates infection, but with some bacteria, this is not the case, so a false negative may occur⁷⁶⁻⁸³.

Molecular Diagnostics

Polymerase-chain reaction (PCR) is one of the most sensitive methods of detecting pathogenic bacteria in human samples. PCR-based assays amplify a specific region of DNA (e.g. 16S rDNA) using a heat-stable DNA polymerase and characterize the amplified region by restriction enzyme digestion (e.g. restriction fragment length polymorphism mapping) or sequencing. PCR performed with urine samples does not display the sensitivity of urine culture. PCR had a sensitivity of 95% for single pathogen UTIs while only a 57% sensitivity for multi-pathogen UTIs⁸⁴⁻⁸⁹.

Treatment

The standard treatment for a UTI is a course of one or more antibiotics. No single antibiotic is recommended for treating every UTI, but nitrofurantoin (Furadantin®), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (Bactrim™), pivmecillinam (Selexid®), fosfomicin trometamol (Monurol®), fluoroquinolone (eg. Cipro®), and betalactam (eg. Augmentin®) may all be used^{67,68}. Although many antibiotics can be used to treat UTIs, one of the main factors that determines which antibiotics are chosen is the bacterial resistance pattern. There are strains of *E. coli* that are resistant to antibiotics and are found throughout the world⁶⁹.

Other strains of bacteria that cause UTIs, including species of *Proteus* and *Klebsiella*, have also developed resistance to specific antibiotics⁹⁰. As a result, the choice of antibiotic is usually governed by susceptibility of the pathogenic organism responsible for an individual's case and/or community history of microbial antibiotic resistance⁹¹⁻⁹⁶. This is typically determined by regional rates reported by local hospitals, although this information can overestimate the prevalence of resistance among bacteria in a region. Some guidelines recommend avoiding a particular antibiotic if local resistance rates to that antibiotic are greater than 20%⁹⁷⁻

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REFERENCES

- Boscia, JA, Kobasa WD, Abrutyn E, Levison ME, Kaplan AM, Kaye D. Lack of association between bacteriuria and symptoms in the elderly. *Am J Med.* 8152(1986).
- Bent S, Nallamotheu BK, Simel DL, Fihn SD, Saint S. Does this woman have an acute uncomplicated urinary tract infection? *JAMA.* 2002; 287:2701-292.
- Jarvis, TR; Chan, L; Gottlieb, T. "Assessment and management of lower urinary tract infection in adults" (PDF). *Australian Prescriber.* 2014; 37 (1), 7-9.
- Salvatore, S; Salvatore, S, Cattoni, E, Siesto, G, Serati, M, Sorice, P, Torella, M . "Urinary tract infections in women." *European journal of obstetrics, gynecology, and reproductive biology.* 2011; 156 (2):131-6.
- Al-Achi, Antoine. An introduction to botanical medicines : history , science, uses, and dangers. Westport, Conn.: *Praeger Publishers.* p. 126(2008).
- Bhat, RG; Katy, TA, Place, FC. "Pediatric urinary tract infections." *Emergency medicine clinics of North America.* 2011; 29 (3): 637-53.
- Flores-Mireles, AL; Walker, JN; Caparon, M; Hultgren, SJ. "Urinary tract infections: epidemiology, mechanisms of infection and treatment options." *Nature reviews. Microbiology.* 2015;13 (5): 269-84.
- Woodford HJ, George J. Diagnosis and management of urinary infections in older peopl. *Clinical Medicine (London).* 2011; 11 (1): 80-3.
- Scholes, D., Hooton, T.M., Roberts, P.L., Stapleton, A.E., Gupta, K., Stamm, W.E. Risk factors for recurrent urinary tract infection in young women. *J Infect Dis;* 182 (4),1177- 82(2000).
- Neumann, I., Fernanda, R. M., Moore, P. Pyelonephritis in non-pregnant women. *Clin Evid* (14),2352-7(2005).
- Dohil R, Roberts, E., Jones, K.V., & Jenkins, H.R.. Constipation and reversible urinary tract abnormalities. *Arch Dis Child* 70(1), 56-7(1994).
- Blethyn, A.J., Jenkins, H.R, Roberts, R. & Verrier Jones, K. Radiological evidence of constipation in urinary tract infection. *Arch Dis Child* 73(6): 534-5(1995).
- Heffner, V., Gorelick, M. Pediatric Urinary Tract Infection. *Clin Ped Emerg Med.* (9), 233-237(2008).
- Perrotta, C., Aznar, M., Mejia, R., Albert, X., Ng, C.W. Oestrogens for preventing recurrent urinary tract infection in postmenopausal women. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* (2):CD005131(2008).
- Foxman, B.. Epidemiology of urinary tract infections: incidence, morbidity, and economic costs. *Am J Med;* 113 Suppl 1A:5-13(2002).
- Nicolle LE."Uncomplicated urinary tract infection in adults including uncomplicated pyelonephritis". *Urol Clin North Am* 35 (1), 1-12(2008).
- Franco, AV . "Recurrent urinary tract infections.". Best practice & research. *Clinical obstetrics & gynaecology* 19 (6), 861-73(2005).
- Dielubanza, EJ and Schaeffer, AJ . "Urinary tract infections in women." *The Medical clinics of North America* 95 (1), 27-41(2011).
- Goldstein, I; Dicks, B; Kim, NN; Hartzell, R . "Multidisciplinary overview of vaginal atrophy and associated genitourinary symptoms in postmenopausal women." *Sexual medicine* 1 (2), 44-53(2013).
- Lipsky, BA . "Prostatitis and urinary tract infection in men: what's new; what's true?". *The American Journal of Medicine* 106 (3), 327-34(1999).
- Ramzan M, Bakhsh S, Salam A. et al. Risk factors in urinary tract infection. *Gomal J Med Sci.*2,50-53(2004).
- Demilie T, Beyene G, Melaku S. et al. Urinary bacterial profile and antibiotic susceptibility pattern among pregnant women in North West Ethiopia. *Ethiop J Health Sci;*22,121-128(2012).
- Colgan, R and Williams, M. "Diagnosis and treatment of acute uncomplicated cystitis." *American family physician* 84 (7),771-6(2011).
- Tortora, G.J. and Derrickson, B. Introduction to the Human Body the essentials of anatomy and physiology, 7th edition. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Turnidge, J., Bell, J., Biedenbach, D.J., Jones, R.N., 2002. Pathogen occurrence and antimicrobial resistance trends among urinary tract infection isolates in the Asia- Western Pacific Region: report from the SENTRY Antimicrobial Surveillance Program, 1998-1999. *Int J Antimicrob Agents;* 20,10-7(2007).
- Hackenhaar A, Albernaz. E. Prevalence and associated factors with hospitalization For treatmentof urinary tract infection during pregnancy. *Rev Bras Ginecol Obstet;*35(5),199-204(2013).
- Phipps, S.; Lim, Y.N.; McClinton, S.; Barry, C.; Rane, A.; N'Dow. Phipps, Simon, ed. "Short term urinary catheter policies following urogenital surgery in adults". *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* (2)(2006).
- Gould CV, Umscheid CA, Agarwal RK, Kuntz G, Pegues DA. "Guideline for prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infections 2009". *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol* 31 (4), 319-26(2010).
- Harris, Richard . "Genitourinary infection and barotrauma as complications of 'P-valve' use in drysuit divers". *Diving and Hyperbaric Medicine : the Journal of the South Pacific Underwater Medicine Society* 39 (4), 210-2(2009).
- Eves, FJ and Rivera, N. "Prevention of urinary tract infections in persons with spinal cord injury in home health care." *Home healthcare nurse* 28 (4),230-41(2010).

30. Almeida PF, Pokorny A. Mechanisms of antimicrobial, cytolytic, and cell-penetrating peptides: from kinetics to thermodynamics.
37. Dugan AS, Maginnis MS, Jordan JA, Gasparovic ML, Manley K, Page R, et al. Human alpha-defensins inhibit BK virus infection by aggregating virions and blocking binding to host cells. *J Biol Chem*. 283,31125-32(2008).
38. Furci L, Baldan R, Bianchini V, Trovato A, Ossi C, Cichero P, et al. New role for human alpha-defensin 5 in the fight against hypervirulent *Clostridium difficile* strains. *Infect Immun* 2015;83,986-95.
39. Spencer JD, Hains DS, Porter E, Bevins CL, DiRosario J, Becknell B, et al. Human alpha defensin 5 expression in the human kidney and urinary tract. *PLoS One*;7:e31712(2012).
40. MacRedmond R, Greene C, Taggart CC, McElvaney N, O'Neill S. Respiratory epithelial cells require Toll-like receptor 4 for induction of human beta-defensin 2 by lipopolysaccharide. *Respir Res*;6,116(2005).
41. Valore EV, Park CH, Quayle AJ, Wiles KR, McCray PB Jr, Ganz T. Human beta-defensin-1: an antimicrobial peptide, innate immunity, and the normally sterile urinary tract. *J Am Soc Nephrol*. 18,2810-2816(2007).
31. Splith K, Neundorff I. Antimicrobial peptides with cell-penetrating peptide properties and vice versa. *Eur Biophys J*; 40,387-97(2011).
32. Yeaman MR, Yount NY. Mechanisms of antimicrobial peptide action and resistance. *Pharmacol Rev*.55:27-55(2003).
33. Lehrer RI, Lichtenstein AK, Ganz T. Defensins: antimicrobial and cytotoxic peptides of mammalian cells. *Annu Rev Immunol*.11,105-28(1993).
34. Ganz T. Defensins: antimicrobial peptides of innate immunity. *Nat Rev Immunol*.3,710-20(2003).
35. Tikhonov I, Rebenok A, Chyzh A. A study of interleukin-8 and defensins in urine and plasma of patients with pyelonephritis and glomerulonephritis. Lee HM. Expression of cathelicidin in human salivary glands. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* .129:211-4(2003).
36. Kai-Larsen Y, Agerberth B. The role of the multifunctional peptide LL-37 in host defense. *Front Biosci*.13,3760-7(2008).
37. Chromek, M. and A. Brauner . "Antimicrobial mechanisms of the urinary tract." *Journal of molecular medicine* 86(1), 37-47(2008).
38. Weinstein DA, Roy CN, Fleming MD, Loda MF, Wolfsdorf JJ, Andrews NC. Inappropriate expression of hepcidin is associated with iron refractory anemia: implications for the anemia of chronic disease. *Blood* .100,3776-81(2002).
39. Park CH, Valore EV, Waring AJ, Ganz T. Hepcidin, a urinary antimicrobial peptide synthesized in the liver. *Nephrol Dial Transplant* .12,2557-61(1997). *J Biol Chem* ;276,7806-10(2001).
40. antimicrobial peptide of urogenital tissues. *J Clin Invest*;101,1633-42(1998).
41. Schroeder BO, Wu Z, Nuding S, Groscurth S, Marciniowski M, Beisner J, et al. Reduction of disulphide bonds unmasks potent antimicrobial activity of human alpha-defensin 1. *Nature*. 469,41923(2011).
42. Chen YH, Po-Ren Hsueh, Robert E. Badal, Stephen P. Hawser, Daryl J. Hoban, Samuel K. Bouchillon Yuxing Ni, David L. Paterson. Antimicrobial susceptibility profiles of aerobic and facultative Gram-negative bacilli isolated from patients with intra-abdominal infections in the Asia-Pacific region according to currently established susceptibility interpretive criteria. *Journal of Infection*; 62,280291(2011).
43. Agerberth B, Charo J, Werr J, Olsson B, Idali F, Lindbom L, et al. The human antimicrobial and chemotactic peptides LL-37 and alpha-defensins are expressed by specific lymphocyte and monocyte populations. *Blood* .96,3086-93(2000).
44. Harder J, Schroder JM. RNase 7, a novel innate immune defense antimicrobial protein of healthy human skin. *J Biol Chem* .277:46779-84(2002).
45. Abrink M, Larsson E, Gobl A, Hellman L. Expression of lactoferrin in the kidney: implications for innate immunity and iron metabolism. *Kidney Int* 2000;57:2004-10.
46. Berger T, Togawa A, Duncan GS, Elia AJ, You-Ten A, Wakeham A, et al. Lipocalin 2-deficient mice exhibit increased sensitivity to *Escherichia coli* infection but not to ischemia-reperfusion injury. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2006;103:1834-9.
47. Reinhart HH, Spencer JR, Zaki NF, Sobel JD. Quantitation of urinary Tamm-Horsfall protein in children with urinary tract infection. *Eur Urol* 1992;22:194-9.
48. Ohlsson S, Ljungkrantz I, Ohlsson K, Segelmark M, Wieslander J. Novel distribution of the secretory leucocyte proteinase inhibitor in kidney. *Mediators Inflamm* 2001;10: 347-50.
49. Hiemstra PS, Maassen RJ, Stolk J, Heinzl-Wieland R, Steffens GJ, Dijkman JH. Antibacterial activity of antileukoprotease. *Infect Immun* 1996;64:4520-4.
50. Kahlmeter G. An international survey of the antimicrobial susceptibility of pathogens from uncomplicated urinary tract infections: the ECOSENS project. *Journal of antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 2003;51:69-76.
51. Wazait, H.D., Patel, H.R., Veer, V., Kelsy, M., Van Der Meulen, J.H., Miller, R.A., Emberton, M., 2003. Catheter-associated urinary tract infections: prevalence of uropathogens and pattern of antimicrobial resistance in a UK hospital (1996-2001) *BJU. Int.* 91(9): 806-9.

58. Baerheim A, Laerum E. Home-voided urine specimen in women. Diagnostic agreement with clean-catch midstream specimens. *Scand J Prim Health Care*. 1990;8:207–211.
59. Lifshitz E, Kramer L. Outpatient urine culture: does collection technique matter? *Arch Intern Med*. 2000;160:2537–2540.
60. Howes, DS. (2010, September 13). Urinary Tract Infection, Female. eMedicine. Retrieved March 12, 2011, from <http://emedicine.medscape.com/article/778670-overview>.
61. Braunwald, E., Fauci, A.S., Kasper, D.L., Hauser, S.L., Longo, D.L. and Jameson, J.L., 2001. Principles of Internal Medicine. Harrison's 15th ed. Vol. 2., McGraw-Hill, New York USA, 1620- 25p.
62. Cheesbrough, M., 2001. District laboratory practice in tropical countries, Part 2. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom. 105-115p.
63. Wilson, M.L., and Gaido, L., 2004. Laboratory diagnosis of urinary tract infections in adult patients. *Clin Infect Dis*. 38:1150-8.
64. Little P, Turner S, Rumsby K, et al. Developing clinical rules to predict urinary tract infection in primary care settings: sensitivity and specificity of near patient tests (dipsticks) and clinical scores. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2006;56:606–612.
65. Isenberg, H.D. (2004) Clinical microbiology procedures handbook, vol. 1, 2 and 3, 2nded. American Society for Microbiology, Washington, D.C.
66. Lehmann, L. E. S. Hauser, T. Malinka, S. Klaschik, F. Stüber, and M. Book, "Real-time polymerase chain-reaction detection of pathogens is feasible to supplement the diagnostic sequence for urinary tract infections," *BJU Int.*, vol. 106, no. 1, pp. 114–120, Jul. 2010.
67. McKinnell JA, Stollenwerk NS, Jung CW, Miller LG. Nitrofurantoin compares favorably to recommended agents as empirical treatment of uncomplicated urinary tract infections in a decision and cost analysis. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. 2011;86(6):480-488.
68. Gupta, P., Gupta, R. K. & Harjai, K. Multiple virulence factors regulated by quorum sensing may help in establishment and colonisation of urinary tract by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* during experimental urinary tract infection. *Indian J. Med. Microbiol*. 31, 29–33 (2013).
69. Hooton TM. Clinical practice. Uncomplicated urinary tract infection. *The New England journal of medicine*. Mar 15 2012;366(11):1028-1037.
70. Kadhim MJ, Sosa AA, Hameed IH. Evaluation of antibacterial activity and bioactive chemical analysis of *Ocimum basilicum* using Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) techniques. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 127-146.
71. Mohammed GJ, Kadhim MJ, Hussein HM. Characterization of bioactive chemical compounds from *Aspergillus terreus* and evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activity. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 889-905.
72. Hameed IH, Altameme HJ, Idan SA. Artemisia annua: Biochemical products analysis of methanolic aerial parts extract and anti-microbial capacity. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016; 7(2): 1843- 1868.
73. Hussein AO, Mohammed GJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical screening of methanolic dried galls extract of *Quercus infectoria* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 49-59.
74. Sosa AA, Bagi SH, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Euphorbia lathyris* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 109-126.
75. Altameme H J, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical analysis of *Urtica dioica* leaves by fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015a; 7(10): 238-252.
76. Mohammed GJ, Omran AM, Hussein HM. Antibacterial and Phytochemical Analysis of *Piper nigrum* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrum and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 977-996.
77. Hamza LF, Kamal SA, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Penicillium expansum* and evaluating antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(9): 194220.
78. Jasim H, Hussein AO, Hameed IH, Kareem MA. Characterization of alkaloid constitution and evaluation of antimicrobial activity of *Solanum nigrum* using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(4): 56-72.
79. Hadi MY, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Nigella sativa* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 8-24.
80. Hameed IH, Ibraheem IA, Kadhim HJ. Gas chromatography mass spectrum and fouriertransform infrared spectroscopy analysis of methanolic extract of *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (6): 90-106.
81. Shareef HK, Muhammed HJ, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Antibacterial effect of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) roscoe and bioactive chemical analysis using gas

- chromatography mass spectrum. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 20-40.
82. Al-Jassaci MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Secondary Metabolites Analysis of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and Evaluation of Antibacterial Activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 304-315.
83. Mohammed GJ, Al-Jassani MJ, Hameed IH. Antibacterial, Antifungal Activity and Chemical analysis of *Punica grantanum* (Pomegranate peel) using GCMS and FTIR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 480-494.
84. Al-Marzoqi AH, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Cassia angustifolia* and evaluate antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 25-48.
85. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Abu-Serag NA. Analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of two medicinal plants, *Equisetum arvense* and *Alchemilla vulgaris* seed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Malays. Appl. Biol*. 2015b; 44(4): 47-58.
86. Hameed IH, Hamza LF, Kamal SA. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Aspergillus niger* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015b;7(8): 132163.
87. Hameed IH, Hussein HJ, Kareem MA, Hamad NS. Identification of five newly described bioactive chemical compounds in methanolic extract of *Mentha viridis* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (7): 107-125.
88. Hussein HM, Hameed IH, Ibraheem OA. Antimicrobial Activity and spectral chemical analysis of methanolic leaves extract of *Adiantum Capillus-Veneris* using GC-MS and FT-IR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 369-385.
89. Hussein HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Study of chemical composition of *Foeniculum vulgare* using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer and gas chromatography - mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 60-89.
90. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. *In vitro* antibacterial, antifungal and phytochemical analysis of methanolic fruit extract of *Cassia fistula*. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 10-30.
91. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Idan SA, Hadi MY. Biochemical analysis of *Origanum vulgare* seeds by fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015c; 7(9): 221-237.
92. Hussein HM. Determination of phytochemical composition and ten elements content (CD, CA, CR, CO, FE, PB, MG, MN, NI AND ZN) of *CARDARIA DRABA* by GC-MS, FT-IR and AAS technique. *Int. J Pharm Bio Sci*. 2016;7(3): (B) 1009 – 1017.
93. Hussein HM. Analysis of trace heavy metals and volatile chemical compounds of *Lepidium sativum* using atomic absorption spectroscopy, gas chromatography-mass spectrometric and fouriertransform infrared spectroscopy. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016;7(4): 2529 – 2555.
94. Jaddoa HH, Hameed IH, Mohammed GJ. Analysis of volatile metabolites released by *Staphylococcus aureus* using gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry and determination of its antifungal activity. *Orient J Chem*. 2016;32(4).
95. Hameed IH, Salman HD, Mohammed GJ. Evaluation of antifungal and antibacterial activity and analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Cinnamon bark) using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Orient J Chem*. 2016;32(4).
96. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hussein HM. Analysis of bioactive metabolites from *Candida albicans* using (GC-MS) and evaluation of antibacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
97. Ubaid JM, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive compounds of *Tribolium castaneum* and evaluation of anti-bacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
98. Hameed IH, Jebor MA, Ommer AJ, Abdulzahra AI. Haplotype data of mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 11,719–12,184 and evaluate the importance of these positions for forensic genetic purposes in Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(2): 1324-1327.
99. Hameed IH. A new polymorphic positions discovered in mitochondrial DNA hypervariable region HVIII from central and north-central of Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(5): 3250-4.
100. Mohammad A, Imad H. Autosomal STR: From locus information to next generation sequencing technology. *Research Journal of Biotechnology*. 2013.
101. Hameed, I.H., Abdulzahra, A.I., Jebor, M.A., Kqueen, C.Y., Ommer, A.J. Haplotypes and variable position detection in the mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 10,71611,184. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2015.